

ISic1120

Epitaph and relief for Kissos and Tryphon

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2003

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance

Found outside the 'porta sud', in the former Garden of the 'Compagnia di Gesu'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas,
inventory 8705

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 54 cm

Width 34-37 cm

Depth 9.5 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-3: 10-15 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. Κίσσος καὶ Τρύφων οἱ Εἰκαδίου
2. [ταλαίπωρ]οι καὶ ἄωροι χρηστο[ῖ]
3. χαίρετε

Apparatus

Text of IGPalermo no.33

Translation (en)

Kissos and Tryphon, sons of Eikadios, miserable and untimely (in death), good men, farewell!

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491446

EDR 136441

EDCS 39102276

PHI 140604

PHI 175628

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